

GenMIS

Version 1

Description

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is developed in the framework of the project No. No.5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007 "Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia" of the second round of the Consolidation and Governance Change Implementation Grants within Investment 5.2.1.1.i "Research, Development and Consolidation Grants" under Reform 5.2.1.r "Higher Education and Science Excellence and Governance Reform" of Reform and Investment Strand 5.2 of the Latvian Recovery and Resilience Mechanism Plan "Ensuring Change in the Governance Model of Higher Education Institutions", research grant project No. LU-BA-PA-2024/1-0052 "Opportunities and challenges of the application of generative artificial intelligence technologies in the development of social sciences studies and research processes" (project manager: Dr. oec. Aivars Spilbergs, 1st September 2024 – 28 February 2026, 200 000 EUR).

Funder

European Commission | EC

Grant

CFLA/007

Researchers

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Kristine Liepina (0009-0002-6505-0896)

Organizations

BA School of Business and Finance, University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [GenMIS](#)

Description:

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is developed in the framework of the project No. No.5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007 "Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia" of the second round of the Consolidation and Governance Change Implementation Grants within Investment 5.2.1.1.i "Research, Development and Consolidation Grants" under Reform 5.2.1.r "Higher Education and Science Excellence and Governance Reform" of Reform and Investment Strand 5.2 of the Latvian Recovery and Resilience Mechanism Plan "Ensuring Change in the Governance Model of Higher Education Institutions", research grant project No. LU-BA-PA-2024/1-0052 "Opportunities and challenges of the application of generative artificial intelligence technologies in the development of social sciences studies and research processes" (project manager: Dr. oec. Aivars Spilbergs, 1st September 2024 – 28 February 2026, 200 000 EUR).

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Organizations:

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: [European Commission](#) | [EC](#)

Grants: [CFLA/007](#)

Project: [0052](#)

3. License

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4. Templates

Descriptions

WP1: Project Management

This WP ensures effective coordination, monitoring and impact assessment of project activities to achieve the research aim within the specified timeframe. Methods: Project management methodologies will be employed to ensure efficient coordination and oversight of project activities.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Tasks: T1.1. Establish project management structure and communication procedures. T1.2. Develop a detailed project plan with timelines and milestones. T1.3. Allocate resources and responsibilities among the research team. T1.4. Monitor project progress, address any deviations from the plan and assess the impact of the project. T1.5. Establish an international scientific committee to oversee the scientific direction of the project.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

TXT

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

a. 1

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No, I have not considered re-using any of existing data.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The scientific findings of this research project will be useful for all academics of the higher education institutions, including scientists of the Republic of Latvia

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

Data will be made available on request.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Comment:

Until the publication of the obtained results

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Excel or Origin software

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

No

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

2026-02-28

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2027-02-28

1 year after end of the grant project

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Aivars Spilbergs

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall

- Passwords

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

WP-2: Literature review

This WP involves conducting systemic literature reviews to conceptualize further groundwork for the research, identify key themes, and substantiate research gaps. Methods: the comparative content and thematic analyses of literature and policy documents.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

This WP involves conducting systemic literature reviews to conceptualize further groundwork for the research, identify key themes, and substantiate research gaps. Methods: the comparative content and thematic analyses of literature and policy documents.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

I have not considered re-using any of existing data.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The scientific findings of this research project will be useful for all academics of the higher education institutions, including scientists of the Republic of Latvia.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

Data will be made available on request.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Till end of project

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Word, Excel

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

No

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivatives 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2026-02-28

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2027-02-28

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

1 year after end of the grant project

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

WP-3: Preparation of survey questionnaire, pilot test

This WP involves development of the structure of the questionnaire, formulation and clarification of the survey questions, selection of the rating scale and pilot test of the questionnaire to assess the quality of the questionnaire before the main survey.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

This WP involves development of the structure of the questionnaire, formulation and clarification of the survey questions, selection of the rating scale and pilot test of the questionnaire to assess the quality of the questionnaire before the main survey.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- PDF
- XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

We have not considered re-using any of existing data.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The scientific findings of this research project will be useful for all academics of the higher education institutions, including scientists of the Republic of Latvia

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Word, Excel

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

No

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivatives 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2026-02-28

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2027-02-28

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

1 year after end of the grant project

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

WP-4: Conducting survey

This WP involves sending out the questionnaire, tracking survey and resending the questionnaire in order to ensure the required number of respondents for further statistical analysis.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

This WP involves sending out the questionnaire, tracking survey and resending the questionnaire in order to ensure the required number of respondents for further statistical analysis.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Survey data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- CSV
- SAV

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

We have not considered re-using any of existing data.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The scientific findings of this research project will be useful for all academics of the higher education institutions, including scientists of the Republic of Latvia

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

CERIF (Common European Research Information Format)

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Until the publication of the obtained results.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

SPSS, Excel

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

No

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2026-02-28

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2027-02-28

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2024-01-01

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

WP-5: Statistical analysis of survey results

This WP involves quality checks of survey responses, assessment of the reliability and validity, identification of the key factors influencing the choice of students and researchers to use GAIT in the study and research process, assessment of significant differences in the intention to use GAIT by age, level of education, study programme, experience, etc.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

This WP involves quality checks of survey responses, assessment of the reliability and validity, identification of the key factors influencing the choice of students and researchers to use GAIT in the study and research process, assessment of significant differences in the intention to use GAIT by age, level of education, study programme, experience, etc.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Aggregate data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- CSV
- SAV
- XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

We have not considered re-using any of existing data.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The scientific findings of this research project will be useful for all academics of the higher education institutions, including scientists of the Republic of Latvia

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

Data will be made available on request.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Comment:

2027-02-28

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

SPSS, Excel

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

No

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-02-28

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2027-02-28

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

WP-6: Preparation of interview guidelines, list of interviewees

This WP involves development of the interview guidelines, formulation and clarification of the interview's questions and list of interviewees.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

This WP involves development of the interview guidelines, formulation and clarification of the interview's questions and list of interviewees.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

TXT

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

We have not considered re-using any of existing data.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The scientific findings of this research project will be useful for all academics of the higher education institutions, including scientists of the Republic of Latvia.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

Data will be made available on request.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Comment:

Until the publication of the obtained results.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Word, Excel

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

No

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-02-28

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2027-02-28

1 year after end of the grant project

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

WP-7: Conducting expert interviews

This WP involves conducting expert interviews for further analysis.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

This WP involves conducting expert interviews for further analysis.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- PDF

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

10

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

We have not considered re-using any of existing data.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The scientific findings of this research project will be useful for all academics of the higher education institutions, including scientists of the Republic of Latvia.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

CERIF (Common European Research Information Format)

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

Data will be made available on request.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Until the publication of the obtained results.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Word, Excel

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

No

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-02-28

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2027-02-28

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

WP-8: Analysis of results of expert interviews

This WP involves qualitative evaluation of the survey results.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

This WP involves qualitative evaluation of the survey results.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Aggregate data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- PDF
- XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

10

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

We have not considered re-using any of existing data.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The scientific findings of this research project will be useful for all academics of the higher education institutions, including scientists of the Republic of Latvia.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

Data will be made available on request.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Until the publication of the obtained results.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Word, Excel

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

No

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-02-28

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2027-02-28

1 year after end of the grant project

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

WP-9: Development of GAIT application strategy and guidelines

This WP involves development of a strategy for the application of GAIT in social science studies and research.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

This WP involves development of a strategy for the application of GAIT in social science studies and research.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- PDF

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

10

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

We have not considered re-using any of existing data.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The scientific findings of this research project will be useful for all academics of the higher education institutions, including scientists of the Republic of Latvia.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

Data will be made available on request.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Until the publication of the obtained results.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Word

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

No

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

Until the publication of the obtained results.

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-02-28

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2027-02-28

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

WP-10: Research reports, scientific publications, and conference presentations

This WP involves development presentations for Scientific council, abstracts, presentations for scientific conferences, scientific publications and project reports.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

This WP involves development presentations for Scientific council, abstracts, presentations for scientific conferences, scientific publications and project reports.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- PDF

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

We have not considered re-using any of existing data.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The scientific findings of this research project will be useful for all academics of the higher education institutions, including scientists of the Republic of Latvia.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

Data will be made available on request.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Until the publication of the obtained results.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Word

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

No

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

Until the publication of the obtained results.

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-02-28

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2027-02-28

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

WP-11: Dissemination of research results

This WP focuses on disseminating research findings to relevant stakeholders and ensuring their visibility and impact. It involves preparing briefs of research findings, organizing dissemination events, sharing results with the broader community. Methods: Dissemination activities will utilize various communication channels, including conferences, workshops, and other events, media and digital platforms to reach diverse audiences and maximize impact.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

This WP focuses on disseminating research findings to relevant stakeholders and ensuring their visibility and impact. It involves preparing briefs of research findings, organizing dissemination events, sharing results with the broader community. Methods: Dissemination activities will utilize various communication channels, including conferences, workshops, and other events, media and digital platforms to reach diverse audiences and maximize impact.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- PDF
- PNG

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

We have not considered re-using any of existing data.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The scientific findings of this research project will be useful for all academics of the higher education institutions, including scientists of the Republic of Latvia.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

Data will be made available on request.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Until the publication of the obtained results.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Word

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

No

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

Until the publication of the obtained results.

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-02-28

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2027-02-28

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Aivars Spilbergs (0000-0003-2537-8053)

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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